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Preparation and Comparative Studies of some Substituted 4-Thiazolidinones and 2-Azetidinones linked to 1,3,4-Thiadiazole

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4-THIAZOLIDINONE derivatives have been found to possess wide variety of biological activities^{1,2}. 2-Azetidinone and its derivatives also possess wide therapeutic activities³. With a view to get better therapeutic agents, we have undertaken the preparation of 4-thiazolidinone and 2-azetidinone derivatives.

Experimental

Melting points of the compound were determined in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 577 spectrophotometer and uv spectra (MeOH) on a Perkin-Elmer 202 spectrophotometer.

2,5-Diaminothiadiazole¹ and 2-hydroxy-5-methylacetophenone/benzophenone⁴ were prepared by the reported methods.

2,5-Bis(α-methyl-2'-hydroxy-5'-methylbenzal-amino)-1,3,4-thiadiazole (1a): A mixture of 2,5-diamino-1,3,4-thiadiazole and 2-hydroxy-5-methylacetophenone taken 1 : 2 molar ratio in ethanol was refluxed for 2 h. The product thus separated was worked up as usual and crystallised from ethanol, (65%), m.p. 210° (Found: C, 63.01; H, 5.20; N, 14.70. C₂₀H₂₀N₄O₂S requires: C, 63.16; H, 5.26; N, 14.74%); ν_{max} (KBr) 3 200 (bonded OH), 1 670 (N=C) and 1 435, 1 350, 1 195 cm⁻¹ (1,3,4-thiadiazole ring); λ_{max} (MeOH) 262 (log ε 3.65), 315 (3.34) and 365 (3.37).

Similarly, other substituted Schiff bases were prepared (Table 1).

2,5-Bis(α-methyl-2'-(2"-hydroxy-5"-methyl)-5'-H-4'-thiazolidinone-3'-yl)-1,3,4-thiadiazole (2a): A mixture of 1a (0.01 mol) in benzene was refluxed with thioglycolic acid (0.02 mol) on a water-bath for 4 h. The resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol to get 2a, (53%), m.p. 220° (Found: C,

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF SCHIFF BASES (1)*

Sl. no.	R	R'	Mol. formula	M.p. °C	Yield %
1.	CH ₃	H	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ N ₄ O ₂ S	210	65
2.	CH ₃	NO ₂	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₂ S	230	60
3.	CH ₃	Br	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₂ S	201	70
4.	C ₆ H ₅	H	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₂ S	190	67
5.	C ₆ H ₅	NO ₂	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₂ S	185	78
6.	C ₆ H ₅	Br	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₂ S	165	75

*All compounds gave satisfactory elemental analyses.

54.50; H, 4.49; N, 10.57. C₂₀H₁₈N₄O₂S₂ requires: C, 54.58; H, 4.54; N, 10.57%); ν_{max} (KBr) 3 101 (CH), 1 605 (N-C) 1 440, 1 360 and 1 180 (1,3,4-thiadiazole ring) and 1 735 strong (C=O) for thiazolidinone ring system); λ_{max} (MeOH) 270 (log ε 3.40), 330 (3.14) and 380 (3.45).

Similarly, other substituted 4-thiazolidinone derivatives were prepared (Table 2).

2,5-Bis(α-methyl-2'-(2"-hydroxy-5"-methyl)-5'-methyl-4'-thiazolidinone-3'-yl)-1,3,4-thiadiazole (3a): Thiolic acid (0.02 mol) added to a saturated solution of the Schiff base (1a; 0.01 mol) in dry benzene (50 ml) was refluxed for 8 h. The resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol as brown needles (3a; 50%), m.p. 205° (Found: C, 56.05; H, 5.00; N, 10.01. C₂₀H₂₂O₄S₂ requires: C, 56.11; H, 5.03; N, 10.07%); ν_{max} (KBr), 3 050 (OH), 1 615 (N-C), 1 422, 1 365 and 1 190 (1,3,4-thiadiazole ring system), 1 760 and 1 782 cm⁻¹ (C=O of thiazolidinone ring system); λ_{max} (MeOH) 261 (log ε 3.14), 327 (3.34) and 375 (3.50).

Similarly, other substituted 4-thiazolidinone derivatives were prepared (Table 2).

2,5-Bis(α-methyl-2'-(2"-hydroxy-5"-methyl)-5'-carboxymethyl-4'-thiazolidinone-3'-yl)-1,3,4-thiadiazole: 1a (0.01 mol) was condensed with thiomalic acid

TABLE 2—PHYSICAL DATA OF 4-THIAZOLIDINONE DERIVATIVES (2, 3)*

Sl. no.	R	R'	R"	Mol. formula	M.p. °C	Yield %
1.	OH ₂	H	H	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₂ S ₂	220	53
2.	OH ₂	NO ₂	H	C ₁₀ H ₈ N ₂ O ₂ S ₂	215	57
3.	OH ₂	Br	H	C ₁₀ H ₉ N ₂ O ₂ S ₂ Br	212	60
4.	C ₆ H ₅	H	H	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₂ S ₂	222	65
5.	C ₆ H ₅	NO ₂	H	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₂ S ₂	230	60
6.	C ₆ H ₅	Br	H	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₂ O ₂ S ₂ Br	228	55
7.	OH ₂	H	OH ₂	C ₁₀ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₂ S ₂	205	50
8.	OH ₂	NO ₂	OH ₂	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₂ S ₂	227	55
9.	OH ₂	Br	OH ₂	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₂ S ₂ Br	242	55
10.	C ₆ H ₅	H	OH ₂	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₂ S ₂	260	60
11.	C ₆ H ₅	NO ₂	OH ₂	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₂ S ₂	225	63
12.	C ₆ H ₅	Br	OH ₂	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₂ O ₂ S ₂ Br	232	57
13.	OH ₂	H	OH ₂ COOH	C ₁₀ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₂ S ₂	230	45
14.	OH ₂	NO ₂	OH ₂ COOH	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₂ S ₂	287	47
15.	OH ₂	Br	OH ₂ COOH	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₂ S ₂ Br	275	55
16.	C ₆ H ₅	H	OH ₂ COOH	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₂ S ₂	293	60
17.	C ₆ H ₅	NO ₂	OH ₂ COOH	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₂ S ₂	270	57
18.	C ₆ H ₅	Br	OH ₂ COOH	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₂ O ₂ S ₂ Br	227	60

*All compounds gave satisfactory elemental analyses.

TABLE 3—PHYSICAL DATA OF 2-AZETIDINONE DERIVATIVES (4)*

Sl. no.	R	R'	Mol. formula	M.p. °C	Yield %
1.	OH ₂	H	C ₆ H ₆ N ₂ O ₂ SOCl ₂	190	60
2.	OH ₂	NO ₂	C ₆ H ₄ N ₂ O ₂ SOCl ₂	185	55
3.	OH ₂	Br	C ₆ H ₅ N ₂ O ₂ SOCl ₂ Br	200	65
4.	C ₆ H ₅	H	C ₁₂ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₂ SOCl ₂	205	62
5.	C ₆ H ₅	NO ₂	C ₁₂ H ₈ N ₂ O ₂ SOCl ₂	211	60
6.	C ₆ H ₅	Br	C ₁₂ H ₉ N ₂ O ₂ SOCl ₂ Br	218	55

*All compounds gave satisfactory elemental analyses.

S. aureus and gram-negative bacteria, *E. coli* and *S. typhoso*. The testing was carried out in dioxan at a concentration of 10 mg ml⁻¹. The compounds were active at concentration of 10 mg ml⁻¹ which is however a low activity. The details of assay reports are not reported.

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(0.02 mol) in presence of anhydrous ZnCl₂ (0.5 g) at 160° for 30 min. The resulting solid was dissolved in sodium bicarbonate, reprecipitated with acid and crystallised from ethanol as pale yellow needles (4a; 45%), m.p. 280° (Found: C, 52.12; H, 4.30; N, 8.63. C₁₀H₁₀N₂O₂S₂ requires: C, 52.17; H, 4.34; N, 8.69%); ν_{max} (KBr) (O-H) (broad) stretching at 3 080 br (OH), 1 595 (N-C), 1 405, 1 330 and 1 175 (1,3,4-thiadiazole ring system), 1 730 and 1 772 cm⁻¹ (C=O for thiazolidinone ring system); λ_{max} (MeOH) 212 (log ε 30.13), 350 (3 40) and 395 (3 27).

Similarly, other substituted 4-thiazolidinone derivatives were prepared (Table 1).

2,5-Bis(α-methyl-3'-chloro-4'-(2"-hydroxy-5"-methyl)-2'-azetidinone-1'-yl)-1,3,4-thiadiazole (4a): A mixture of 1a (1.0 mol) and triethylamine (1.0 mol) in dioxan (25 ml) was stirred well by gradual dropwise addition of monochloroacetyl chloride (0.015 mol) at room temperature. The mixture was stirred for 5 h and left at room temperature for 3 days. The precipitates of triethylamine hydrochloride was filtered and washed with dioxan. The filtrate was treated with anhydrous magnesium sulphate and the solvent removed under reduced pressure. The resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol to get 5a (60%), m.p. 190° (Found: C, 54.00; H, 4.07; N, 10.43. C₂₄H₂₂N₄O₄SOCl₂ requires: C, 54.03; H, 4.12; N, 10.50); ν_{max} (KBr) 2 905 br (OH), 1 670 (C-O), 1 760 (β-lactum ring system), 1 450, 1 320 (1,3,4-thiadiazole ring system), 1 190 and 700 cm⁻¹ (C-Cl); λ_{max} (MeOH) 310 (log ε 3.51) and 390 (3.70).

Similarly, other substituted 2-azetidinone derivatives were prepared (Table 3).

Antibacterial activity: The Schiff bases and their 2-azetidinone and thiazolidinone derivatives were screened for antibacterial activity by cup-plate method⁶ using gram-positive bacterium

Structure and Stereochemistry of Mollugogenol-G – A Triterpenoid Sapogenin from *Mollugo hirta*

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A number of triterpenoid saponins and sapogenins have earlier been reported from this laboratory from *Mollugo hirta*¹ and *Mollugo spargula*². The present communication reports the isolation of a new triterpenoid sapogenin called mollugogenol-G, the structure of which has been established as 3β,16β,22-trihydroxy-21α-H-hop-5-ene (1a). The